

Characterizing Time-Resolved Motion of the Scolopidium and Its Role in The Gating Mechanism of Insect Auditory Transduction

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Abstract. Insect auditory transduction occurs within a scolopidium—a multicellular unit comprised of one or two auditory neurons enclosed in a supporting cell called the scolopale cell. In a tympanic ear, the apical end of the scolopidium is embedded in a cap cell that connects the scolopidium in series to the tympanum. The mechanism by which vibrations at the tympanum elicit the transducing current in the scolopidium remains highly speculative due to the absence of direct observation of sound-evoked motion in the scolopidium. In this study, we examined scolopidia from auditory neurons in ex-vivo preparations of Müller’s organ obtained from the desert locust, *Schistocerca gregaria*. We used Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) to characterize background motions of Müller’s organ in the region where the scolopidia is located. Subsequently, we employed a CMOS-based high-photon efficiency (capturing 95% of photons), high-speed camera to characterize the relative motion within the scolopidium at about ten thousand frames per second in response to sound stimulation from 1 to 5 kHz. The characterization of the relative motion within the scolopidium was achieved by subtracting the background motion of Müller’s organ using image processing techniques. The obtained characterization reveals the complex motions of Müller’s organ itself and that of the scolopidium, implicating the role of these motions in locust auditory transduction. Additionally, we propose a possible gating mechanism of insect auditory transduction based on these observations.

INTRODUCTION

All animal ears, whether vertebrate or insect, serve the same fundamental purpose: converting sound-induced vibrations into electrical signals. Insect hearing can match or even exceed the performance of their vertebrate counterparts in certain aspects. For example, a species of moth can detect sound frequencies ten times higher than those humans can perceive ¹. Unfortunately, understanding of insect auditory transduction still lags behind that of vertebrates.

The sensory unit responsible for insect auditory transduction is the scolopidium, an elongated multicellular unit that contains a single cilium. For 60 years, since the first images of insect sensory cilia were captured ², the scolopidium has been assumed to be the site of mechano-electrical transduction ³. However, the exact mechanism by which the scolopidium moves and how this motion results in the gating of the auditory transduction channel remains speculative. This is because the cilia are inaccessible for live microscopic imaging, their movements are too subtle to be resolved optically, and recordings of transduction channel currents in auditory neurons are limited to locusts, which lack genetic manipulations of the channels.

The scolopidia are classified into three groups based on the maximal sensitivity of their auditory neurons: Group 1 (0.5-1.5 kHz but also 3.5 kHz, ~20 cells), Group 2 (10-25 kHz, ~13 cells), and Group 3 (2.5-4 kHz, ~45 cells)⁷. The cilium, approximately 10 μm long, responds to sound frequencies ranging from a few Hz to tens of kHz. Mechanical

measurements from the cricket's auditory organ have made indirect inferences about the cilium's response, suggesting tilting of its tip⁴ and complex multi-modal movements involving 3D elliptical motions relative to the base⁵. Furthermore, the pioneering work of Stephen and Bennet-Clark on the sound-evoked motion of Müller's organ, using stroboscopic photography, suggested large phase-lags (60°–120°) or anti-phasic motion in different parts of Müller's organ, potentially causing straining in the tissue and thus of the scolopidia⁶. These hypotheses provide valuable insights into the macroscopic performance of the auditory organ but lack the spatial resolution to image the scolopidium and the cilium directly. Real-time imaging of the cilium during sound stimulation is crucial for understanding the gating mechanism.

In this study, we investigated the sound-evoked motion of Müller's organ and the scolopidium in adult desert locusts (*Schistocerca gregaria*, Fig. 1a-c). We employed Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) to measure the sound-evoked vibrations of Müller's organ along two different axes: the antero-posterior axis (normal to the tympanum surface) and the meso-lateral axis (tangential to the tympanum surface, specifically the side-to-side motion of Müller's organ). Additionally, we studied scolopidium motion using a high-speed camera, allowing us for the first time to observe the real-time movement of the scolopidium upon sound stimulation. We found that the motion of Müller's organ measured with OCT results in elliptical motion of the scolopidium in both Group-1 and Group-3 scolopidia. Despite the complexity of this motion, it is predominantly characterized by pulling along the ciliary axis, which we speculate opens the auditory transduction channels.

METHODS

Locust Husbandry and Sample Preparation

Desert locusts (*Schistocerca gregaria*) were raised in crowded conditions under a 12:12-hour light-dark cycle at temperatures ranging from 25°C to 36°C. Their diet consisted of fresh wheat and bran. Male locusts between 10 and 20 days post-imaginal molt were used for all experiments.

For our experiments, the locust ears were excised and affixed to a plastic dish with a 3 mm hole. The speaker was placed facing the external surface of the tympanum while the internal surface was immersed in extracellular saline. There were two configurations: (1) a horizontal preparation where the tympanum was glued flat over the hole (Fig. 2a – top panel), and (2) a vertical preparation where the tympanum was glued to a flat wall of the dish (Fig. 2a – bottom panel). The extracellular saline contained 185 mM NaCl, 10 mM KCl, 2 mM MgCl₂, 2 mM CaCl₂, 10 mM HEPES, 10 mM trehalose, and 10 mM glucose.

Optical Coherent Tomography Vibrometry

Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) is an imaging technique based on low-coherence interferometry. We used a spectral domain-OCT system (Ganymede, Thorlabs) for interferometric imaging and vibration measurements. The field of view was 10×10 mm, with a depth range of 3.5 mm. Acquisitions were externally triggered using monophasic rectangular pulses phase-locked to the acoustic stimulation system (Tucker Davies Technologies System III) at a sampling rate of 90 kHz.

The OCT beam was manually aligned, optimizing vibration measurements along the beam's orientation, while underrepresenting out-of-axis motion (Fig. 2a). The beam always originated from the top, with preparations mounted either horizontally or vertically. Vibrations were analysed using Fourier transformation of the vibration waveforms derived from contiguous groups of three pixels in each scan. Each frequency component in a vibration measurement was assessed for phase-locking significance using the Rayleigh test ($p=0.001$). Data acquisition and analysis were performed using a custom-made MATLAB (2007, MathWorks) toolbox developed by Marcel van der Heijden.

High-speed Camera Imaging

We recorded the sound-evoked response motion of the scolopidium using a high-speed camera (KINETIK, Teledyne) mounted on an FN1 Nikon upright microscope. With a region of interest of 100x300 pixels (at 60x magnification, 32.4 x 10.8 μm) and sufficient lighting, we achieved a maximum acquisition rate of approximately 9,000 frames per second. Sound stimulation was synchronized with the imaging and delivered through a speaker (Visaton FR 10 HM, RS Components) using an analogue-digital converter (National Instrument, PCIe 6323).

The sound pressure level was calibrated by measuring the voltage output of an amplified microphone (Clio PRE-01 and Clio MIC-03, Audiomatica) in response to a 94 dB SPL 1 kHz tone from a sound level calibrator (Cal73, Brüel & Kjær). This calibration allowed us to calculate the sound pressure level based on the microphone's voltage output. The microphone was then placed where the excised locust ear would be during experiments, and the voltages delivered to the speaker were adjusted to produce a flat response across the stimulated frequency range (1–5 kHz). The setup was controlled by an in-house MATLAB graphical user interface.

For high-speed camera imaging, we always mounted the tympanum in a horizontal configuration (similar to Fig. 2a – top panel) but with an oblique angle to imitate the orientation of the tympanum *in vivo* (Fig. 1a).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Positions of the Group 3 Scolopidia

Although we are interested in the mechanism underlying mechano-electrical transduction in all three groups of auditory neurons, we focus on mapping the positions of Group 3 scolopidia because they are the majority (45 out of 80 cells) and are spread over a larger area. In contrast, Group 1 and Group 2 scolopidia are fewer and confined to small regions near the folded body and at the base of the fusiform body, respectively.

FIGURE 1. The locust's Müller's organ and its auditory transduction unit: **(a)** The desert locust *Schistocerca gregaria* possesses a pair of Müller's organs internally attached to the tympanic membranes on either side of the abdomen. The inset shows the tympanic membrane, typically hidden beneath the wings. The dark ridge (arrowhead) indicates the area where Müller's organ is located. Anatomical references are based on the locust's body. **(b)** A schematic of the right tympanic membrane viewed from inside the body. **(c)** A schematic of Müller's organ showing the location of the scolopidia, which are classified into three groups based on the maximal sensitivity of their auditory neurons: Group 1 (0.5-1.5 kHz but also 3.5 kHz, ~20 cells), Group 2 (10-25 kHz, ~13 cells), and Group 3 (2.5-4 kHz, ~45 cells). **(d)** Ensembled normalized positions of Group 3 scolopidia from 16 ears. The positions are normalized between the two largest widths of the ganglion and the styliform body. The inset shows an auditory neuron filled with a neural tracer, neurobiotin, in the area of a scolopidium. The scale bars are 50 mm (a), 5 mm (a-inset), and 10 μ m (d-inset).

We labelled auditory neurons by back-filling patch pipettes with a neural tracer, neurobiotin. The tracer was delivered via the auditory nerves (for the protocol, see ⁸). Neurobiotin labels the entire length of the auditory neuron

from the cell body in the ganglion to the distal end where the scolopidium is located. Although the scolopidia themselves were not usually labelled, the bulbous structure of the dendrite, known as dendrite dilation, was clearly visible in all preparations. We mapped the positions of the Group 3 scolopidia using the dendrite dilations, which are located $11.1 \pm 3.7 \mu\text{m}$ ($N = 20$ ears, $n = 46$ cells) away from the base of the scolopidium. We found that the scolopidia are situated about 60% of the distance from the ganglion towards the styliform body, measured from the maximal widths of Müller's organ (Figure d). We speculate that strong relative motion in this region is necessary to elicit mechano-electrical transduction.

Sound-Evoked Motion of Müller's Organ Is Tuned Differently Across Axes

We used Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) to investigate the sound-evoked motion of the entire Müller's organ ($N = 18$ ears). First, we mounted the tympanum flat on a dish with the external side facing the speaker (Fig. 2a, top panel). In this orientation (antero-posterior axis), the vibration measured was predominantly normal to the tympanum surface, as the OCT beam can only measure motion along its axis. We found that the vibration magnitude was strongest at 1 kHz and 4 kHz (Fig. 2b, top panel, grey lines), consistent with previous laser vibrometer measurements of the whole tympanum⁹.

At 1 kHz, Müller's organ vibrates uniformly in phase. However, at 4 kHz, a traveling wave with abrupt changes in both magnitude and phase is observed near the scolopidia (Fig. 2c-d). The complex magnitude difference, considering both magnitude and phase between two positions across this transition (marked * and o in Fig. 2c), indicates a peak frequency of 4 kHz (Fig. 2b, top panel, black line). At this frequency, the styliform body moves in phase with the tympanum, while the ganglion shows a phase lag of approximately one-third of a cycle (Fig. 2d – top panel).

Next, we mounted the tympanum using a vertical preparation (Fig. 2a, bottom panel), where the motion along this orientation (meso-lateral axis) is dominated by side-to-side movement of Müller's organ, tangential to the tympanum surface. In this orientation, the vibration magnitude peaks at 2.5 kHz, with complex magnitude differences producing peaks at 2.5 and 3.5 kHz. The side-to-side motion was twice as large as the up-and-down motion (Fig. 2b), and no vibration was detected between 4-5 kHz. Similar abrupt transitions in vibration magnitude and phase lag of one-third of a cycle were observed in the middle of Müller's organ at the peak frequencies of 2.5 and 3.5 kHz (Fig. 2c, Fig 2d – bottom panel).

Although we cannot simultaneously register motion in both axes, the larger side-to-side motion combined with the smaller up-and-down motion of Müller's organ likely produces a complex circular motion. This indicates that mechano-electrical transduction utilizes a complex motion pattern of Müller's organ that cannot be defined by movement along a single axis alone. This complexity is further suggested by the fact that the tuning curves from motion in each individual axis do not match the broad tuning curves measured from spike counts and mechano-electrical transduction currents reported in previous studies^{7,10}.

Pulling and Elliptical Motion of the Scolopidium Along the Ciliary Axis

We further assessed the motion of the scolopidium in Group 1 ($N = 7$ ears, $n = 15$ cells) and Group 3 ($N = 6$ ears, $n = 18$ cells) using high-speed camera imaging. The tympanum was mounted in a flat preparation at an oblique angle. Without sound stimulation, the scolopidium and its basal body were in a relaxed state with a slight bend at the base. Upon sound stimulation, the scolopidium was pulled along the ciliary axis in a cycle-by-cycle manner (Fig. 2e). While there was slight in-and-out-of-plane motion, the motion along the ciliary axis was the most pronounced. We suspect that this motion along the ciliary axis is crucial for mechano-electrical transduction.

Using the Template Matching plugin in ImageJ, we tracked the motion of the cap cell and found that the scolopidium exhibits elliptical motion. This elliptical motion becomes more pronounced and larger at 1 kHz and 3-4 kHz in both Group 1 and Group 3 scolopidia (Fig. 2f). Despite the elliptical nature of the motion, the movement along the ciliary axis remains the most significant. The peak at 2.5-4 kHz is also broadly tuned, similar to what was observed in mechano-electrical transduction currents¹⁰.

Interestingly, the motion of the scolopidium along the ciliary axis in both Group 1 and Group 3 shows similar sensitivity (Fig. 2g-h). According to electrophysiological recordings¹¹, we expected Group 1 scolopidia to be most sensitive to 1-1.5 kHz and slightly less sensitive at 3-4 kHz, while Group 3 scolopidia were expected to be sensitive only to 3-4 kHz. It is worth noting that the motion observed here includes some background motion. These results are

still preliminary, as we managed to remove background motion and see contrast at the basal part of the scolopidium at this magnification in only a few cells. In the next step, we plan to sacrifice spatial resolution by working at lower magnification, allowing us to use surrounding landmarks to quantify the relative stretching of the ciliary axis.

FIGURE 2. Sound-evoked motion of Müller's organ and the scolopidium: **(a)** Sound stimulation for OCT vibrometry along two axes of Müller's organ: antero-posterior (top panel) and meso-lateral (bottom panel). **(b)** Tuning of the vibration magnitude measured along the antero-posterior (top panel) and meso-lateral axes (bottom panel). **(c)** Vibration maps at the frequencies that evoked maximal vibration shown in (b). **(d)** Vibration magnitude and phase difference along the length of Müller's organ, from the maximal width of the organ at the ganglion (*) to the maximal width at the styliform body (o) in (c). The average position of the scolopidia from Fig. 1d is superimposed here. **(e)** Montage of sound-evoked motion of a Group 1 scolopidium stimulated at 1.5 kHz. The position of the cap cell is indicated (arrowhead). **(f)** Elliptical motion of the scolopidium based on tracking the cap cell. Tuning of the scolopidium motion along the ciliary axis in Group 1 **(g)** and Group 3 **(h)** scolopidia. Scale bars are 200 μm (c) and 5 μm (e).

CONCLUSION

In this study, we investigated the sound-evoked motion of Müller's organ and the scolopidium in the desert locust *Schistocerca gregaria*. Using Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) and high-speed camera imaging, we provided the first direct observations of real-time movement within the scolopidium upon sound stimulation. Our findings indicate that the scolopidium exhibits complex motion patterns, including pronounced elliptical motion and significant pulling along the ciliary axis, which is likely crucial for mechano-electrical transduction.

We observed that the motion of Müller's organ and the scolopidium is tuned differently across axes, with specific frequency sensitivities that align with previous electrophysiological recordings. These insights suggest that mechano-electrical transduction in insect auditory systems relies on intricate motion dynamics that cannot be fully described by single-axis movements alone.

In summary, our results provide a preliminary understanding of the mechanical processes underlying insect auditory transduction and propose a potential gating mechanism based on the observed motion patterns.

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We thank Manuela Nowotny and Marcel van der Heijden for assisting with initial OCT data acquisition and providing the locust. We also thank Daisy Ogle and Alix Blockley for performing fluorescent microscopy of neurobiotin labelling of auditory neurons.

REFERENCES

1. H.M. Moir, J.C. Jackson, and J.F.C. Windmill, "Extremely high frequency sensitivity in a 'simple' ear," *Biol. Lett.* **9**(4), 20130241 (2013).
2. E.G. Gray, "The Fine Structure of the Insect Ear," *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. Lond. B. Biol. Sci.* **243**(700), 75–94 (1960).
3. L.H. Field, and T. Matheson, "Chordotonal Organs of Insects," in *Adv. Insect Physiol.*, edited by P.D. Evans, (Academic Press, 1998), pp. 1–228.
4. J. Hummel, S. Schöneich, M. Kössl, J. Scherberich, B. Hedwig, S. Prinz, and M. Nowotny, "Gating of Acoustic Transducer Channels Is Shaped by Biomechanical Filter Processes," *J. Neurosci. Off. J. Soc. Neurosci.* **36**(8), 2377–2382 (2016).
5. A. Vavakou, J. Scherberich, M. Nowotny, and M. van der Heijden, "Tuned vibration modes in a miniature hearing organ: Insights from the bushcricket," *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **118**(39), e2105234118 (2021).
6. R.O. Stephen, and H.C. Bennet-Clark, "The Anatomical and Mechanical Basis of Stimulation and Frequency Analysis in the Locust Ear," *J. Exp. Biol.* **99**(1), 279–314 (1982).
7. A. Michelsen, "Frequency Discrimination in the Locust Ear by means of Four Groups of Receptor Cells," *Nature* **220**(5167), 585–586 (1968).
8. A. Blockley, D. Ogle, C. Woodrow, F. Montealegre-Z, and B. Warren, "Physiological changes throughout the ear due to age and noise - a longitudinal study," (2021).
9. J.F.C. Windmill, S. Bockenhauer, and D. Robert, "Time-resolved tympanal mechanics of the locust," *J. R. Soc. Interface* **5**(29), 1435–1443 (2008).
10. B. Warren, and M. Nowotny, "Bridging the Gap Between Mammal and Insect Ears – A Comparative and Evolutionary View of Sound-Reception," *Front. Ecol. Evol.* **9**, 667218 (2021).
11. A. Michelsen, "The physiology of the locust ear: I. Frequency sensitivity of single cells in the isolated ear," *Z. Für Vgl. Physiol.* **71**(1), 49–62 (1971).

QUESTIONS AND COMMENTS

Rebecca Whiley: In the introduction, it's mentioned that locusts "lack genetic manipulations of the channels." I wanted to clarify, does this mean that there is not a genome currently available to manipulate the genes encoding the MET channels?

Atitheb: *There is a genome currently available to manipulate the genes but, until recently, there is no available mutant locusts with genes encoding the MET channels. We are currently developing mutant locusts using CRISPR/Cas.*

Rebecca Whiley: I want to confirm my understanding of how the cilia respond to stimulation, particularly your identification of the tuning of cilia. Did you use the degree of deflection (i.e., how much the cilia move at a given stimulating frequency) to identify frequencies to which they were most sensitive?

Atitheb: *We looked at how much the cilia move (displacement) at a given stimulating frequency. We have not looked at the degree of deflection but we plan to also look at other parameters.*

Rebecca Whiley: Could you elaborate a bit more on the suspected role of the ciliary motion on opening MET channels?

Atitheb: We think the cilia are stretched upon sound stimulation and the stretching, in turn, opens the MET channels.

Rebecca Whiley: A few comments:

I would suggest moving the first paragraph in the results section ("Positions of the Group 3 Scolopidia") that explains the classification of scolopidia groups to the introduction. The concepts of Group-1 and Group-3 are introduced in the penultimate sentence of the introduction, but it was unclear what these were until the results.

Near the end of the paragraph on the top of page 4, you reference Figure D — I believe this is 1D?

Also, there is a minor typo in the second paragraph of the introduction. The sentence starting with "yet" is generally repeated in the following sentence starting with "however".

Atitheb: *Thank you very much. I have modified as suggested.*

Martin Goepfert: Do you see any deformation of the scolopale and the cilium?

Atitheb: *We see bending of the scolopidium. Although we cannot always resolve the cilium, we do see in certain frame that the cilium is bent together with the scolopale wall.*

Kalpan Ved: Does Mueller's organ contain efferent neurons?

Atitheb: *To my knowledge, there is no efferent neurons in the locusts but there are in mosquitoes. Martin Goepfert showed that there are efferent neurons in the mosquitoes and he should be able to answer the question in more details.*